

Professional Competence And Its Components Of The Future Logoped Teacher

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Abstract: --.

Keywords — ---.

INTRODUCTION.

The promising civilization of any society is attached to its educational status, a new composition and essence, teran marifiy-culture. Already, only a high level of training is the only factor that ensures the future of society, the state and the nation, determines the prestige of the world.

Currently, the only goal of our state is to establish a humane, democratic-exclusive society, as well as to raise it to the upper stages of socio-economic and cultural development, to take a worthy place in the ranks of the world community. The orientation serves to fulfill noble goals. The fact that these goals have a positive result, first of all, scientific knowledge to the younger generation depends on the careful teaching of the basics, the formation of a broad worldview in them, the effective organization of educational work on the formation of manic-moral qualities. The creation of a Porlock perspective of the land of Zero, the widespread dissemination of its name, the demonstration of the national-cultural heritage created by the great-grandchildren to society, the ensuring that the developed countries of our independent republic occupy a place depends on the upbringing of the younger generation as a perfect person and a qualified specialist.

Social determines that attention should be paid to the preparation of future specialists for professional activities in ensuring that the owners of professions operating in different spheres of life know and operate in accordance with specific professional laws.

In pedagogical science, the Explanatory Dictionary gives the following explanation of the term "profession". "The profession is a type of human activity that, as a result of special training and work experience, acquires a complex of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications for the implementation of professional activities in a particular health, providing it with physical capabilities, mental abilities and legal rights."

Issues related to the choice of profession and the formation of professional activity are covered in the research work of several pedagogical scientists. Including;

- Prof. J.Khasanboev focuses on professional activity in the training of future specialists and defines professional activity as follows: professional function - belonging to a graduate of

the relevant educational institutions, is the activity of being able to operate in the sphere that an individual occupies in life, mastering his knowledge within the framework of his profession and practically introducing them without deviations. Professor M.Ochilov in his work "teacher's etiquette" gives the opinion that "people who are engaged in a certain area of activity are also called such a moral profession (professional) morality, which has certain moral norms and requirements." The scientist emphasizes the need to educate high moral qualities in the preparation of future educators for professional activities. A. In his study, holikov argues that the teaching profession, based on the essence of the content, "the pedagogical profession is a stable system of socially significant qualities that are driving as a perfect person." B.X. In his study, Rakhimov studied the professional cultural relations of future educators and teachers. In his opinion: "professional Cultural Relations Act as the main tool in achieving a solution of interpersonal, positive relations and serve to improve the functioning of the individual." Professor N.Muslimov, in his doctoral dissertation, gives opinions on the organization of professional activities of specialists, stating the following points: "the presence of personal professional qualities is expressed through an indicator of its formation as a specialist. The process of organizing the professional activity of a specialist is carried out in sequence at certain stages".

S.Bozorova, in her monograph "vocational-oriented teaching technology in Higher Education", defines vocational training technology as: "a technology that shapes skills and competencies that ensure that learners fulfill important personal qualities for their future professional activities, as well as functional responsibilities for their task".

Professional training of speech therapists V.K.Orfinskaya, O.V.Pravdina, F.A.Rau, F.F.Rau, M.L.Shklovsky, L.S.Volkova, V.I.Seliverstov, T.B.Filicheva, N.A.Cheveleva, G.V.Chirkina, S.I.Shakhovskaya, F.Kadyrova, F.Teshaboeva, M.Mahmudova, L.Khayitov, O.Bozorov, H.Muzaffarovalarniing became an object of research.

Despite the importance of the study, the authors reduce the multifactorial process of the professional development of future logoped to arming it with an orderly set of knowledge, skills and qualifications. Thus, traditional approaches and principles that affect certain aspects of the development of professional competence essentially affect the future professional activity in the process of preparing future

logopeds, determining the criteria for assessing the readiness of students, future logopeds.

O.In assessing the level of methodological competence of the future speech therapist in his scientific work, Bozorov's knowledge of the field is considered as one of the relevant criteria. As criteria(indicators) that determine the knowledge of future logopeds, the following can be distinguished: the appropriation of knowledge about the content and specificity of corrective-logopedic activity; logopedic and methodological knowledge; knowledge of the essence of methodological competence and the principles of its formation (cognitive component).

In order to show their personality in the corrective-logopedic process, the future logoped must concentrate on certain qualifications. The indicators of this criterion are reflected in the following skills: sybjt-sybjt-specific mynosabatlap kissing skills; skills of self-reflection from a pedagogical bias; skills of being able to perform methodological activities(components related to activity), which are embedded in Universal and personal values. Reflects the concept of methodological competence of the future speech therapist in a holistic arrangement of affective, cognitive and activity-related components in close connection with each other.

L.Khayitov explained that the professional competence of speech-theoretical knowledge and practical kunikmas, personality qualities are a complex dressing, formed on the basis of social experience; it is a certain ability to perform various professional diagnostic, methodological, psychological, corrective, social tasks, which are integrated into the completion of nutk disorders and the social empowerment of children with such disorders.

Ya. Chicherina, D. Nurkeldieva and E. Bondarevas 'monograph"innovative approaches to building future defectologists - personnel" developed a competent model for developing professional creativity in future defectologists. Proposed by the authors

based on the general structure of the innovation model of preparing future defectologists for professional activities, the forms of Organization of organizational learning-cognitive falsity of students from the audience (scientific research, pedagogical practice, independent professional activity, voluntarianism, etc.k).

L.Khayitov emphasizes the components of the socio - pedagogical competence of the future defectologist as follows: socio-personal, cognitive, professionally active, analytical-reflexive . The set of components of socio - pedagogical competence provides the opportunity to achieve the level of professional activity and support for personal self-realization of the future speech therapist.

O on the topic of developing the competence of future logopeds based on innovative technologies.V.In the work of Saprionova, the question of the implementation of ideas about the deontological analysis, criteria, moral qualities of the future

speech therapist in the process of corrective work on the elimination of speech disorders was studied.

In creating the necessary conditions for the formation of an educational environment in educational institutions aimed at the training of highly qualified specialists, it is necessary to improve and develop their professional competency based on the study of the needs and capabilities of teachers, and motivation plays a special role in this process.

Motives are also of particular importance in the processes of development of professional competency, since they depend on the effectiveness of the process of professional education and educational relations, expressing the effectiveness of the processes of development of professional competency.

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